

Towards a greener and circular scrap-based steel production

Introducing 100% scrap-based Electric Arc Furnace (EAF) steel products into mass-market

CiSMA aims to introduce **100% scrap-based Electric Arc Furnace (EAF) steel products** into mass-market steel sheet consumer goods, currently manufactured through the integrated Blast Furnace – Basic Oxygen Converter route.

The project will help **cut CO₂ emissions, boost circular economy and reduce EU's foreign dependency on critical raw materials** in key European sectors such as the automotive, laundry equipment, white goods and other engineering industries.

PARTNERS:

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Circular Steel for Mass Market Applications

Introducing scrap-based Electric Arc Furnace (EAF) steel for a greener circular economy in mass-market sheet metal goods

www.cisma-project.eu

Up to 100% of scrap charges

Four recycled high-performance steel products with up to 100% scrap, contributing to the reduction of EU's foreign dependency on raw materials

75% reduced greenhouse gas emissions

Steel manufacturing via EAF, reducing significantly CO₂ emissions compared to traditional blast furnace processes

Green climate-neutral steel products

Recycled EAF steels integrated in components from the automotive and commercial laundry solutions industries

Demonstrating the 100% recycled steels in mass-market products

Volvo Cars Automotive

High-strength steel for a vehicle door sill

High-formability steel for components such as a cross-member

Electrolux Professional Industrial laundry

Interstitial-free steel tested in professional laundry equipment front panels

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CiSMA will help to cut down emissions in steel production by more than 75% and use up to 100% percent scrap loads

Enabling technologies

EAF-based, scrap-intensive steelmaking characterisation

Advanced characterisation through synchrotron and Atom Probe Tomography

Scrap analysis and improvement

Implementation of an automated separation of low-quality scrap for improving the steel stream

Novel tests and enabling tools

Toolbox including fast characterisation tests for fracture toughness, forming embrittlement and fatigue evaluation, two online material testing methods, and data-driven modelling and digital tools